

Comparison of subject classification systems for resources in Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

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1 Overview

[Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\)](#) is an integrated data infrastructure that directly supports researchers in the physical sciences in the UK to manage, transform and share their data. It is a project funded by the [Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council \(EPSRC\)](#) and developed by the [Sciences and Technology Facilities Council \(STFC\)](#) and the [University of Southampton](#). The first version of its outputs was released in spring 2025.

The aim of this document is to review options to choose a [dcat:themeTaxonomy](#) (taxonomy/vocabulary/ontology/classification system) to describe the [dcat:theme](#) (subject/ research topic/ scientific discipline) of PSDI [resource themes](#) and [resources](#) in the PSDI resource catalogue. This will be used:

1. In the DCAT metadata which describes the catalogue of resources and resource themes <https://metadata.psdi.ac.uk/psdi-dcat.jsonld>
2. In the [PSDI What We Provide](#) resource catalogue to facilitate resource filtering and add tags to resource pages
3. In the [PSDI Cross Data Search](#) to facilitate data source filtering

To avoid confusion with the PSDI term [resource theme](#) we will either refer to this field explicitly as `dcat:theme` or “subject” in this document (rather than just “theme”).

While PSDI does capture `dcat:theme` values for its resources currently, this work is to investigate whether other classification system options offer any benefits over this, and to apply additional hierarchical grouping to guide users when filtering resources and datasets by subject.

1.1 Current subject classification in PSDI

PSDI are currently using [EuroSciVoc](#) to classify subject of resources and resource themes:

- in the jsonld representation of the PSDI resource catalogue:
 - `dcat:theme` in <https://metadata.psdi.ac.uk/psdi-dcat.jsonld>

```
"dcat:theme": {
  "skos:prefLabel": "physical sciences",
  "@type": "skos:Concept",
  "@id": "http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/d3b09b78-ac5c-4fc3-b58a-9573daf0e304"
}
```

- in the [PSDI What We Provide](#) website representation of the PSDI resource catalogue - in its filters which are populated by the jsonld representation. Currently, the subject filter simply displays the labels of these EuroSciVoc concepts themselves in a list without any of its hierarchy or grouping:

Figure 1.1.2 Subject filter in [PSDI resource themes webpage](#)

- in the resource webpages of the [PSDI What We Provide](#) resource catalogue the matching EuroSciVoc term is displayed with a link to its EuroSciVoc persistent identifier (PID):

Figure 1.1.2 [Example PSDI resource landing page](#) showing linked `dc:theme` terms (`dc:term` values are linked to the PID for the term)

Note that PSDI resource themes and resources are tagged according to the terms which describe them best, regardless of their level of the EuroSciVoc hierarchy.

This work will enable the following improvements to PSDI:

- ensuring that the classification system used is as intuitive as possible for resource owners to find relevant terms to tag their resources
- grouping of subject filters in the [PSDI What We Provide](#) web pages (in Figure 1.1.2 above) – currently the exact terms that apply to the resources are shown in a list, without any hierarchy or grouping, which will become unwieldy as PSDI grows and there are more resources with more subjects
- applying this grouping to enable filtering of data sets in the [PSDI Cross Data Search](#). Figure 1.1.3 shows that only simple text filtering is applied currently. Grouped, hierarchical filtering of data sources (consistent with that in the PSDI resource catalogue) would be of benefit to the user.

Figure 1.1.3 Current data source selection in the [PSDI Cross Data Search](#)

1.2 PSDI subject classification requirements

The following are **must-have requirements** for a subject classification system for dcat:theme in PSDI:

1. Intuitive: the classification system needs to be straightforward for resource-owners and PSDI users to understand and navigate.
2. Physical Sciences scope: the classification system needs to include the whole scope of PSDI. We broadly align this with the [Remit, programmes and priorities](#) of the [Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council \(EPSRC\)](#): chemistry; engineering; information and communications technologies; materials; mathematical sciences; physics, but in line with their policy some research areas that are slightly peripheral may also be included.
3. Maintained and versioned: the classification system will need to be updated as research and its focuses evolve and develop. This should be done in a managed way, so that the classification system as a whole needs to be versioned, as do individual terms - legacy terms should be preserved but flagged and any new terms should be linked to replaced terms where appropriate.
4. Hierarchical: some level of hierarchy and grouping into one or more levels make it easier to navigate to find applicable terms and can provide different levels of classification detail as required.

The following are **nice-to-have requirements** for a classification system for dcat:theme in PSDI:

1. PIDs (persistent identifiers): terms that describe dcat:theme need to have a PID (to persistently and uniquely identify each term, ideally as an Internationalized Resource Identifier (IRI)) but this is indicated as "nice to have", because if a chosen classification system does not have PIDs we could formalise an existing classification system into a PSDI [SKOS Simple Knowledge Organization System Reference](#) vocabulary with PIDs and maintain this ourselves.
2. Definitions: term definitions will make navigation and choice of terms clearer. Term definitions of subject terms can be useful in clarifying their scope but can be complex to write and

interpret, so we have classed this as a nice-to-have requirement since if the subject term names or labels are chosen carefully, these can be easier to process.

3. Adoption: if the subject classification system is used in other organisations, repositories, reports, analyses etc. then it would help PSDI's interoperability. This is classed as a nice-to-have requirement because mappings and cross-walks can be developed and used to increase interoperability (although we acknowledge that these can be complex and it is not always possible to define one-to-one relationships for all terms).

1.3 Subject classification selection process

The process to select a subject classification to capture dcat:theme of PSDI resources (as described in this document) involved the following steps:

- Review a wide range of subject classification candidates and for each provide a summary, an evaluation against the requirements above and outcomes or further actions, in particular whether it should be shortlisted (see section [2 All classification system candidates](#)).
- For candidates shortlisted in the previous step, PSDI version 1 resource themes and PSDI domain categories are mapped onto their terms as further evaluation of intuitiveness and suitability (see section [3 Mapping of PSDI resource themes onto shortlisted candidates](#)).
- Final ranking of shortlisted candidates and next steps (see section [4 Conclusions](#)).

2 All classification system candidates

We attempted to investigate a wide range of subject classification systems. For context, we start with the [PSDI domain categories](#) (an in-house categorisation of domains used by PSDI). Then, [OECD \(Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development\) FORD \(Fields of Research and Development\)/FOS \(Fields of Study\)](#) is described since this is a widely accepted and adopted subject categorisation. This categorisation frames the top-level structure of [EuroSciVoc](#) (which is currently used to capture dcat:theme in PSDI) and here we describe why this was the first shortlisted candidate. The other two shortlisted candidates are described next: [Modern Science Ontology \(modsci\)](#), and [OpenAlex Topics](#).

We then move onto subject classifications which were not shortlisted but were reviewed. Like OECD FORD/FOS, the [UNESCO \(United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization\) nomenclature for fields of science and technology](#) is commonly used worldwide to classify research and funding on a national and international level. [MeSH \(Medical Subject Headings\)](#) and [NCI \(National Cancer Institute\) Thesaurus \(NCIt\)](#) are vocabularies that are widely used for US life sciences public resource categorisation (and beyond). The next 5 subject classifications are used by funding bodies of various kinds to categorise research funded by them and its outputs: [EPSRC \(Engineering and Physical Sciences Council\)](#), [ERC \(European Research Council\)](#), [DFG \(Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft\)](#), [Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification \(ANZSRC\)](#), and [the Royal Society](#). [Nature](#) are academic publishers who use classification systems to group their outputs on a journal and article level. The [nfdiCoreOntology](#) captures academic discipline on a high level and are a useful point of comparison, since it was developed by [NFDI](#) who are in many ways the German equivalent of PSDI (since they are the national infrastructure for scientific research data in Germany). Then as a final point of comparison, various [higher education teaching](#) and [library](#) classification systems were listed.

2.1 PSDI domain categories

Figure 2.1.1 PSDI domain categories

Summary:

- Derived in-house by PSDI (see [Appendix 1](#) for more details).
- Categories of Physical Science derived from analysis of: [Institution of Chemical Engineers \(IChemE\) special interest groups](#); [Royal Society of Chemistry \(RSC\) interest groups](#); [Institute of Physics \(IOP\) special interest groups](#); and [Royal Society of Chemistry \(RSC\) journals](#). These were grouped together and assigned names as described in Appendix 1.

- Used previously in PSDI to categorise funding applications and to ensure a wide representation of stakeholders for the PSDI advisory board.
- See Appendix 2 for a mapping of PSDI resource themes (as of summer 2025) to these PSDI domain categories.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Simple and intuitive. The terms correspond to active communities in the physical sciences that researchers are familiar with.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes – matches PSDI scope exactly. Quite chemistry focussed.
- Maintained and versioned: Not yet (PSDI would need to do this).
- Hierarchical: Single level with no hierarchy. To be more useful for PSDI, it would need a categorisation layer above it (to group the 18 categories into higher level disciplines) and more detailed field definitions within each of them.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Not yet. It would need to be converted into a SKOS vocabulary that is published and maintained by us and could be updated as required.
- Definitions: Not yet (PSDI would need to do this). This would help with some ambiguity in terms e.g.
 - “Chemistry Materials” makes sense when in context with “Engineering Materials” but the term isn’t commonly used otherwise.
 - The distinction between “Sustainability & Energy” and “Environmental” is subtle.
 - “Methods” is somewhat ambiguous and would need careful definition.
- Adoption: Not used by other repositories, so less interoperable than other candidates, unless mapping to them is implemented.

Other considerations:

- This classification has been used by PSDI in the past and would provide a level of consistency with other PSDI processes and language.
- We would have full control over the terms and their definitions to fit to PSDI’s purposes.

Outcome:

- Not shortlisted because of the requirements that are not met.
- If these PSDI domain categories are still regarded as useful in the future in parallel with the final chosen categorisation system, then the terms of both should be mapped.

2.2 OECD FORD (Fields of Research and Development)/Fields of Study (FOS)

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- 1. Natural Sciences
 - 1.1 Mathematics
 - 1.2 Computer and information sciences
 - 1.3 Physical sciences
 - 1.4 Chemical sciences
 - 1.5 Earth and related environmental sciences
 - 1.6 Biological sciences
 - 1.7 Other natural sciences
- 2. Engineering and Technology
 - 2.1 Civil engineering
 - 2.2 Electrical engineering, electronic engineering, information engineering
 - 2.3 Mechanical engineering
 - 2.4 Chemical engineering
 - 2.5 Materials engineering
 - 2.6 Medical engineering
 - 2.7 Environmental engineering
 - 2.8 Environmental biotechnology
 - 2.9 Industrial Biotechnology
 - 2.10 Nano-technology
 - 2.11 Other engineering and technologies
- 3. Medical and Health Sciences
 - ...
- 4. Agricultural Sciences
 - ...
- 5. Social Sciences
 - ...
- 6. Humanities
 - ...

Latest full list is available at:

- “ANNEX 2 COMPARISON OF THE REVISED FOS CLASSIFICATION WITH THAT IN FM 2002”, page 12, of [FOS.pdf](#) which is available for download from [Revised Field of Science and Technology \(FOS\) classification in the Frascati Manual - EconStatKB - UN Statistics Wiki](#).

Summary:

- The FORD (Fields of Research and Development) as defined by the [Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development \(OECD\)](#) in the Frascati Manual, which was first published in 1963.
- The latest (2015) version of the Frascati manual is [OECD's 2015 Frascati Manual](#) and in this:
 - The fields are given on page 59 in “Table 2.2. Fields of R&D classification” which lists 6 main “Broad Classification” values e.g. “1. Natural Sciences” with a column which lists “Second-level classification” values for each these e.g. “1.1 Mathematics”, “1.2 Computer and information sciences” etc.
 - This categorisation makes some interesting observations about fields of research or study categorisation:
 - The complex classification process for research field is highlighted by the observation on page 58 of the manual that it is based on:
 - The knowledge sources drawn upon for the R&D activity carried out.
 - The objects of interest.
 - The methods, techniques and professional profiles of the scientists.
 - The areas of application.

- Another consideration when categorising research is outlined on page 45 which explains the difference between “Basic research”, “Applied research” and “Experimental development” in certain example fields (with examples in various fields in pages that follow).
- The fields were updated in 2021 in [Revised Field of Science and Technology \(FOS\) classification in the Frascati Manual - EconStatKB - UN Statistics Wiki](#). This document has some more granular classifications (but these are more illustrative examples rather than an exhaustive list with no identifiers for them).

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: simple and intuitive (the result of much research and thought):
 - The report describes the well-considered research and thought that went into the derivation of this classification system.
 - One limitation of this classification is that it uses the terms “physical sciences” and a separate neighbouring term “chemical sciences” which are broadly equivalent to “physics” and “chemistry” respectively (maybe with a slightly wider scope). “Physical sciences” defined in this way is a somewhat confusing category in the context of PSDI, where “physical sciences” is used as a broader term which includes “physics” and “chemistry”. Most resources in the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure would not be categorised as “physical sciences”.
 - This classification system is not granular enough for use in PSDI directly (all version 1 PSDI resources would belong to only four categories: “1.3 Physical sciences”; “1.4 Chemical sciences”; “2.4 Chemical engineering”; “2.5 Materials engineering” or “2.10 Nano-technology”).
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes in breadth, but not granular enough.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes, updated periodically. Last released 2021.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 2 levels.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Not as such, but numbered for reference.
- Definitions: Not formal definitions (but some examples given in accompanying report).
- Adoption: Very well accepted and broadly adopted - used as the basis for many studies and reports e.g. from funders and governments. It is also used by Dryad <https://datadryad.org/> to allow users to filter data to subjects of relevance, and [DMPOnline](#), an online Data Management Plan creation tool developed by the [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#) so that researchers can pick what guidance, options and templates are available based on their specified research discipline.

Outcome:

- Not suitable for PSDI directly because it is not granular enough.

2.3 EuroSciVoc

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- social sciences
 - ...
- natural sciences
 - earth and related environmental sciences
 - ...
 - mathematics
 - ...
 - biological sciences
 - ...
 - chemical sciences
 - organic chemistry
 - ...
 - inorganic chemistry
 - ...
 - nuclear chemistry
 - ...
 - electrochemistry
 - ...
 - physical chemistry
 - thermochemistry
 - photochemistry
 - quantum chemistry
 - polymer sciences
 - ...
 - catalysis
 - ...
 - analytical chemistry
 - ...
 - physical sciences
 - ...
- engineering and technology
 - ...
- humanities
 - ...
- agricultural sciences
 - ...
- medical and health sciences
 - ...

Full list is available:

- For download from <http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/>.
- For browsing at <https://op.europa.eu/en/web/eu-vocabularies/concept-scheme/-/resource?uri=http://data.europa.eu/8mn/euroscivoc/40c0f173-baa3-48a3-9fe6-d6e8fb366a00>.

Summary:

- Multilingual taxonomy of science fields based on OECD FORD (Fields of Research and Development) but extended in granularity through a semi-automatic process developed with Natural Language Processing (NLP) techniques with content from [CORDIS](#) (a repository of EU research results).

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes on the whole but we note:

- Some of PSDI's initial Pathfinders (partner projects) struggled to find appropriate tags using this classification system.
- As discussed in the previous assessment of OECD FORD/FOS (which is used for the top-levels of this classification), most of PSDI is not in "Physical sciences" because they are in the neighbouring category "Chemical sciences", which is not ideal.
- It is somewhat complicated to navigate with some portions of the hierarchy being 5 levels deep and others being 3 levels deep.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: Maintained and versioned (currently on version 1.6.0).
- Hierarchical: Yes – up to 5 levels.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Yes.
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Used by European Union to classify and search for research projects in the CORDIS repository. Compatible with OECD FORD which is very widely adopted.

Other considerations:

- EuroSciVoc Makes OECD FORD more useful to PSDI by: (1) adding extra level of subject detail (2) and making it semantic with PIDs and hierarchical.
- Multilanguage (German, English, Spanish, French, Italian, and Polish).

Outcome:

- Shortlisted- see [section 3.1](#) for mapping of PSDI resource themes onto these EuroSciVoc categories.
- If adopted, the hierarchy used in resource catalogue filtering will need to be simplified to make it easier to find resources.

2.4 Modern Science Ontology (modsci)

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

Full list is available at:

- <https://w3id.org/skgo/modsci#ModernScience> in its raw form (best viewed with [Protégé ontology editor](#)).
- or via portals for browsing e.g. [modsci:Chemistry on NFDI4ING terminology service](#).

Summary:

- Modern Science Ontology (ModSci) is an upper ontology for providing a taxonomy of research fields, or fields of science. It provides a hierarchical classification of various entities such as publications, events and scientists' research fields.
- Its background is described in [An Upper Ontology for Modern Science Branches and Related Entities](#) in which Figure 1 shows that it is a complex classification system that captures “Modern Science” subjects in their context of linked Phenomenon, Application of Science, Scientific Instrument, Scientist, Scientific Method etc.
- Subject classifications are part of the [Science](#) class.
- It uses Field of Research (FoR) by ANZSRC (as described in [section 2.12](#)) and draws on other existing classification systems too, but does have some differences from these.
- Chemistry is in “Natural Sciences” which are defined as follows: “The natural sciences are those branches of empirical science that produce a comprehension of the natural world through the use of data collected from it by observation and measurement to construct deterministic and/or stochastic quantitative models of its phenomena”.
- But Engineering is in “Applied Sciences” which is defined as “Applied science is the use or the study of the use of scientific knowledge to develop technology.” And Engineering only has one sub-topic (Biological Engineering).

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes on the whole with the following notes:
 - Multi-hierarchical e.g. “Biochemistry” appears under both “Biology”, and “Chemistry”.
 - Some areas (e.g. contents of “Computer Science”) are less finished than others – there are terms without labels which appear at different levels of the hierarchy (e.g. “Natural Language Processing (NLP)”).
 - Chemistry is very well represented.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes – with caveats:
 - Maintained in [github repository](#) (last commit August 2024).
 - Does not look like it is in active development, but PSDI could consider contributing to its development if required.
- Hierarchical: Yes.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Yes.
- Definitions: Some limited definitions.
- Adoption: Yes:
 - Used in Stuart Chalk’s [SciData - A Scientific Data Model](#) schema:
 - In the context: "w3i": "https://w3id.org/skgo/modsci#",
 - In the data: "discipline": "w3i:Chemistry", and "subdiscipline": "w3i:Crystallography",
 - Some other classes (not “Science” though) are used by NFDI e.g. in [The MatWerk ontology](#).

Other considerations:

- Good semantic grounding ([Basic Formal Ontology \(BFO\)](#)-compliant).

Outcomes:

- Shortlisted- see [section 3.2](#) for mapping of PSDI resource themes onto these domain categories.

2.5 OpenAlex Topics

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- Health Sciences
 - ...
- Life Sciences
 - ...
- Physical Sciences
 - Chemical Engineering
 - ...
 - Chemistry
 - Analytical Chemistry
 - ...
 - Electrochemistry
 - ...
 - Inorganic Chemistry
 - ...
 - Organic Chemistry
 - ...
 - Physical and Theoretical Chemistry
 - Various Chemistry Research Topics
 - thermodynamics and calorimetric analyses
 - Photochemistry and Electron Transfer Studies
 - History and advancements in chemistry
 - Electrostatics and Colloid Interactions
 - Crystallography and molecular interactions
 - Chemical Reactions and Mechanisms
 - Advanced Physical and Chemical Molecular Interactions
 - Spectroscopy
 - ...
 - Computer Science
 - ...
 - Earth and Planetary Sciences
 - ...
 - Energy
 - ...
 - Engineering
 - ...
 - Environmental Science
 - ...
 - Materials Science
 - ...
 - Mathematics
 - ...
 - Physics and Astronomy
 - ...
- Social Sciences
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- [OpenAlex topic mapping table.xlsx](#) (domains, fields subfields and topics).

Summary:

- Originated from “Fields of study taxonomy” within “Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG)” (hierarchical topic tree) which was retired in December 2021.
- [OpenAlex](#) is an index of scientific publications and related data. The [topics](#) in it are used for their categorisation.
- Github repository <https://github.com/ourresearch/openalex-topic-classification>. shows how to run LLM code and model to assign “Topic” based on title and abstract. PSDI could use this code (or similar) to provide a tool for tagging resources or resource themes.

- Topic classification based on LLM code can be unreliable so if we were to use it in PSDI we would need the human-in-the-loop to curate suggested topic assignments.
- The topic classification is described in the white paper [OpenAlex: End-to-End Process for Topic Classification](#).

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes on the whole with the following notes:
 - Top levels of Domains > Fields > Subfields are very well organised – this is from the [All Science Journal Classifications \(ASJC\)](#) used to organise publications in [Elsevier's Scopus](#). A useful feature that was noted in this classification (although it does not carry through to OpenAlex topics) was the inclusion of a “Multidisciplinary” category – this is a good way to describe resources which do not correspond to a specific field, subfield or topic but are applicable to a wide range of them that many classification systems don't have.
 - The most detailed level of the hierarchy “Topics” in OpenAlex is very detailed and specific. There are 1571 topics within Physical Sciences – this large number could make it hard to navigate and assign them unless this is automated.
 - Very similar topics can be found in very different parts of the hierarchy, e.g. if “crystallography” is entered in a search, 4 topics in 3 different subfields are returned – this could be a good thing (multiple routes to the same resources) but could be confusing and result in a resource being hard to find when browsing down:
 - 16 Chemistry > 1606 Physical and Theoretical Chemistry > 10798 Crystallography and molecular interactions
 - 25 Materials Science > 2505 Materials Chemistry > 11878 Solid-state spectroscopy and crystallography
 - 25 Materials Science > 2505 Materials Chemistry > 12613 X-ray Diffraction in Crystallography
 - 31 Physics and Astronomy > 3104 Condensed Matter Physics > 12762 Crystallography and Radiation Phenomena
 - The best description for crystallography (10464 Crystal structures of chemical compounds) sits under 1604 Inorganic Chemistry rather than Organic chemistry or their containing category, which is not in line with most of PSDI's crystallography resources.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: Maintained but individual terms do not look like they're versioned:
 - Original version was released in 2022 and it is being updated and refined. While this is positive, we note that e.g. the topic named “Scientific Computing and Data Management” was called “Management and Reproducibility of Scientific Workflows” in the OpenAlex topics data downloaded in September 2024 (https://github.com/lambdamusic/openalex-hacks/blob/main/src/data/openalex_topics_2024_09.json). There is no record of previous topic labels in the topic page <https://openalex.org/topics/T11986> or its json API representation api.openalex.org/topics/T11986. As such, PSDI would need to maintain a versioned of OpenAlex terms in a SKOS vocabulary which would need to be updated automatically and regularly.
- Hierarchical: Yes. 4, very consistent, well-organised layers.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Yes - there are PIDs for topics (e.g. <https://openalex.org/topics/T10464>), domains (e.g. <https://openalex.org/domains/3>), fields (e.g. <https://openalex.org/fields/16>) and subfields (e.g. <https://openalex.org/subfields/2505>) and these are mapped to Wikipedia and wikidata equivalents.
- Definitions: Yes, also very descriptive titles and keywords and linked Wikipedia pages.
- Adoption: Used by OpenAlex.

Other considerations:

- A third party ([Unpacking OpenAlex topics classification | Blogs | Michele Pasin](#)) has converted the equivalent of this data, obtained using the [OpenAlex API](#) into a SKOS vocabulary available at lambdamusic.github.io/openalex-hacks/ontology/openalex-topics-rdf.ttl using open source code available at <https://github.com/lambdamusic/openalex-hacks> - this demonstrates the possibility of producing, hosting and maintaining a SKOS version of the topics and their categorisation which is what PSDI would need to do to use this.

Outcome:

- Shortlisted - see [section 3.3](#) for mapping of PSDI resource themes onto these domain categories.
- If PSDI were to use it to capture dcat:theme we would need to set up:
 - a pipeline to formalise these topics and their hierarchy into a SKOS vocabulary with versioning, definitions and PIDs (and with mapping to our PSDI domains - see 3.3) which is regularly run and updated.
 - a service (based on an OpenAlex open source LLM model and code) to suggest topics which are relevant to a PSDI resource, which are then subject to human review before adding approved terms as dcat:theme values of the PSDI resource catalogue for them.
 - a pipeline to update the term labels in the PSDI resource catalogue if they change in the source.

2.6 UNESCO nomenclature for fields of science and technology

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- 11 Logic
 - ...
- 12 Mathematics
 - ...
- 21 Astronomy and astrophysics
 - ...
- 22 Physics
 - ...
- 23 Chemistry
 - 2301 Analytical Chemistry
 - 2301.01 Absorption spectroscopy
 - 2301.02 Biochemical analysis
 - 2301.03 Chromatographic analysis
 - 2301.04 Electrochemical Analysis
 - 2301.05 Emission spectroscopy
 - 2301.06 Fluorimetry
 - 2301.07 Gravimetry
 - 2301.08 Infrared spectroscopy
 - 2301.09 Magnetic resonance spectroscopy
 - 2301.10 Mass spectroscopy
 - 2301.11 Microchemical analysis
 - 2301.12 Microscopy
 - 2301.13 Microwave spectroscopy
 - 2301.14 Phosphorimetry
 - 2301.15 Polymer analysis
 - 2301.16 Radiochemical analysis
 - 2301.17 Raman spectroscopy
 - 2301.18 Thermal analytical methods
 - 2301.19 Volumetry
 - 2301.20 X-Ray spectroscopy
 - 2301.99 Other (specify)
 - 2302 Biochemistry
 - ...
 - 2303 Inorganic chemistry
 - ...
 - 2304 Macromolecular chemistry
 - ...
 - 2305 Nuclear Chemistry
 - ...
 - 2306 Organic Chemistry
 - ...
 - 2307 Physical chemistry
 - ...
 - 2390 Pharmaceutical chemistry
 - ...
 - 2399 Other chemical specialties (specify)
 - ...
- 24 Life Sciences
 - ...
- 25 Earth and Space Sciences
 - ...
- 31 Agricultural Sciences
 - ...
- 32 Medical Sciences
 - ...
- 33 Technological Sciences
 - ...
- 51 Anthropology
 - ...
- ...

Full list is available at:

- [SKOS: Download](#) (2007 version) for download in Turtle or RDF format.
- or can be browsed at [Hierarchical Browsing of SKOS: UNESCO nomenclature for fields of science and technology](#).

Summary:

- Developed by [UNESCO \(United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization\)](#).
- According to [SKOS: UNESCO nomenclature for fields of science and technology](#):
 - The Proposed international standard nomenclature for fields of science and technology was proposed in 1973 and 1974 by the Division of Science Policy and Statistics for Science and Technology of UNESCO and adopted by the Scientific Advisory Committee. This is a classification system widely used in knowledge management of research projects and dissertations. Categories are divided into three hierarchical levels:
 - Fields: Referring to general sections. Encoded with two digits and comprises several disciplines.
 - Disciplines: Provide an overview of specialty groups in Science and Technology. Encoded with four digits. Despite being different from each other disciplines with cross references, or within the same field, are considered to have common characteristics.
 - Subdisciplines: Entries are the more specific elements of the nomenclature and represent the activities that take place within a discipline. Encoded with six digits. In turn, must correspond to individual specialties in science and technology.
 - There is top-level 2-digit grouping, then 4-digit grouping within this then 6-digit within that. PSDI resources would need to be mapped down to the 6-digit level of granularity.
 - Multi-hierarchical - Physical chemistry is in it twice – under physics and under chemistry.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes with limitations:
 - Top level seems more intuitive than EuroSciVoc.
 - Very physics-based for subjects which PSDI might think of as chemistry (very limited range of chemistry subjects).
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: No – does not look like it's been updated since 1970's.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 2 digit, 4 digit and 6 digit levels of classification.
- PIDs (persistent identifiers): Yes.
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Widely used for classification of research papers and doctoral dissertations.

Outcome:

- Not shortlisted because it is not being updated, and its limited description of chemistry compared to EuroSciVoc (although we could learn from its arrangement of top-level subjects which are easier to navigate).

2.7 MeSH (Medical Subject Headings)

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- ...
- Disciplines and Occupations [H]
 - Natural Science Disciplines [H01]
 - Biological Science Disciplines [H01.158]
 - Chemistry [H01.181]
 - Biochemistry [H01.181.122]
 - ...
 - Cheminformatics [H01.181.169]
 - Chemistry, Agricultural [H01.181.216]
 - Chemistry, Analytic [H01.181.309]
 - Chemistry, Clinical [H01.181.341]
 - Chemistry, Inorganic [H01.181.370]
 - ...
 - Chemistry, Organic [H01.181.404]
 - Chemistry, Pharmaceutical [H01.181.466]
 - Chemistry, Physical [H01.181.529]
 - Crystallography [H01.181.529.240]
 - Electrochemistry [H01.181.529.307]
 - Photochemistry [H01.181.529.711]
 - Radiochemistry [H01.181.529.776]
 - Computational Chemistry [H01.181.590]
 - Microchemistry [H01.181.650]
 - Earth Sciences [H01.277]
 - Environmental Science [H01.345]
 - Materials Science [H01.413]
 - Mathematics [H01.548]
 - Microtechnology [H01.570]
 - Nanotechnology [H01.603]
 - Physics [H01.671]
 - Science [H01.770]
 - Health Occupations [H02]
- ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html> for download.
- <https://meshb.nlm.nih.gov/treeView> for browsing.

Summary:

- <https://www.nlm.nih.gov/mesh/meshhome.html> says “The Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) thesaurus is a controlled and hierarchically-organized vocabulary produced by the National Library of Medicine. It is used for indexing, cataloging, and searching of biomedical and health-related information. MeSH includes the subject headings appearing in MEDLINE/PubMed, the NLM Catalog, and other NLM databases.”.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: The disciplines that are included are organised intuitively, but there are omissions due to the life-science focus of mesh (see notes about Scope).
- Physical Sciences scope: Does not cover the whole of the Physical Sciences scope of PSDI:
 - It is not very granular (e.g. “Materials Science [H01.413]” and “Chemistry, Organic [H01.181.404]” are not broken down into more detail.
 - “Engineering” is not included.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes.

- Hierarchical: Yes.
- PIDs: Yes.
- Definitions: Yes.
- Adoption: Yes used widely in the life sciences, and North America.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because the wider context of MESH tends to skew its focus to life sciences rather than physical sciences, it does not cover the full scope of PSDI and does not describe it in sufficient detail for our purposes.

2.8 NCI (National Cancer Institute) Thesaurus (NCIt)

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- C16328 Behavioral Sciences
 - ...
- C16344 Biological Sciences
 - ...
- C15178 Complementary and Alternative Medicine
 - ...
- C84341 Discovery Science
 - ...
- C26037 Food Safety
 - ...
- C19199 Health Sciences
 - ...
- C157884 Integrative Medicine
 - ...
- C45427 Medical Science
 - ...
- C148247 Natural and Applied Sciences
 - ...
- C25193 Occupation
 - ...
- C16987 Physical Sciences
 - C16414 Chemistry
 - C16415 Analytical Chemistry
 - C18470 Computational Chemistry
 - C18794 Fiber Chemistry
 - C16713 Immunochemistry
 - C16418 Inorganic Chemistry
 - C16419 Organic Chemistry
 - C16421 Physical Chemistry
 - C19130 Chemical Dynamics
 - C18122 Chemical Kinetics
 - C16985 Photochemistry
 - C19048 Structural Chemistry
 - C18188 Stereochemistry
 - C64351 Surface Chemistry
 - C20609 Synthesis Chemistry
 - C16633 Geography
 - ...
 - C16825 Mathematics
 - ...
 - C16989 Physics
 - ...
- C19491 Population Sciences
 - ...
- C17141 Social Sciences
 - ...
- C17187 Technology
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://evsexplore.semantics.cancer.gov/evsexplore/hierarchy/ncit/C19160> for browsing "Occupation or Discipline (Code - C19160)".

Summary:

- Thesaurus from [NCI \(National Cancer Institute\)](#).

- As described at that webpage: “NCI Thesaurus (NCIt) provides reference terminology for many NCI and other systems. It covers vocabulary for clinical care, translational and basic research, and public information and administrative activities.”.
- Scientific subjects (stored under [Occupation or Discipline \(Code - C19160 \)](#)) are only a small part of this thesaurus – it contains a wide range of other concepts and definitions used in life sciences.
- Most PSDI resources fall under the category “Physical Sciences” but some will also fall under its adjacent category: “Technology” (under its subcategories “Engineering”, “Nanotechnology”, “Computer Sciences”, “Food Science and Technology”). “Engineering” for example contains subjects such as: “Bioengineering”, “Chemical Engineering”, “Electrical Engineering”, “Environmental Engineering”.
- More granular than [MeSH](#) and more of an overlap with PSDI’s scope

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes.
- Physical Sciences scope: Better representation of the Physical Sciences than MESH but focus is biomedical, and some key PSDI areas are not well represented e.g. [C16418 - Inorganic Chemistry](#) only contains one sub-category [C16416 - Bioinorganic Chemistry](#).
- Maintained and versioned: Yes.
- Hierarchical: Yes.
- PIDs: Yes.
- Definitions: Yes.
- Adoption: Yes used widely in the life sciences, and North America.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because its wider context skews its focus to life sciences rather than physical sciences, so it is lacking in detail about some areas of interest to PSDI.

2.9 EPSRC (Engineering and Physical Sciences Council) research areas

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- Algebra
- Analytical science
- Antihydrogen
- Architectures and operating systems
- Artificial intelligence technologies
- Assistive technology, rehabilitation and musculoskeletal biomechanics
- Bioenergy
- Biological informatics
- Biomaterials and tissue engineering
- Biophysics and soft matter physics
- Built environment
- Carbon capture and storage
- Catalysis
- Chemical biology and biological chemistry
- Chemical reaction dynamics and mechanisms
- Clinical technologies (excluding imaging)
- Coastal and waterway engineering
- Cold atoms and molecules
- Combustion engineering
- Complex fluids and rheology
- Computational and theoretical chemistry
- Condensed matter: electronic structure
- Condensed matter: magnetism and magnetic materials
- Continuum mechanics
- Control engineering
- ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/EPSRC-140223-ResearchAreasList-1.pdf>.
- And <https://www.ukri.org/what-we-do/browse-our-areas-of-investment-and-support/?category=epsrc>.

Summary:

- Developed by [EPSRC \(Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council\)](#) to categorise research funded by them.
- EPSRC research strategies are informed by a range of evidence sources: <https://www.ukri.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/EPSRC-13062022-EPSRC-Evidence-Sources-amended.docx>.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Very difficult to find relevant terms because there are 108 terms with no organisation of hierarchy, listed in alphabetical order.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes – matches PSDI scope exactly.
- Maintained and versioned: This categorisation is primarily focussed on funding policy so there is a risk that when it is updated it may be completely different. There is no guarantee that it will be of a similar form with any analogous, versioned, mapped terms.
- Hierarchical: Single level with no hierarchy.
- PIDs: No PIDs – not semantic and no identifier numbers.
- Definitions: Yes.

- Adoption: Yes – used in a different context for EPSRC research categorisation – reporting and grant allocation. Researchers who are PSDI contributors and users may have used this classification already when applying for grants.

Other considerations:

- Matches scope and funding of PSDI - synergy with PSDI funding.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because of the work that would be required to convert it into a semantic form with PIDs, especially considering that not all requirements have been met and the high risk that this effort would need to be repeated in the future if the EPSRC categorise their research in a different way.

2.10 ERC (European Research Council) panel structure for Physical Sciences and Engineering

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- Physical Sciences and Engineering
 - PE1 Mathematics
 - ...
 - PE2 Fundamental Constituents of Matter
 - ...
 - PE3 Condensed Matter Physics
 - ...
 - PE4 Physical and Analytical Chemical Sciences
 - PE4_1 Physical chemistry
 - PE4_2 Spectroscopic and spectrometric techniques
 - PE4_3 Molecular architecture and Structure
 - PE4_4 Surface science and nanostructures
 - PE4_5 Analytical chemistry
 - PE4_6 Chemical physics
 - PE4_7 Chemical instrumentation
 - PE4_8 Electrochemistry, electrodialysis, microfluidics, sensors
 - PE4_9 Method development in chemistry
 - PE4_10 Heterogeneous catalysis
 - PE4_11 Physical chemistry of biological systems
 - PE4_12 Chemical reactions: mechanisms, dynamics, kinetics and catalytic reactions
 - PE4_13 Theoretical and computational chemistry
 - PE4_14 Radiation and Nuclear chemistry
 - PE4_15 Photochemistry
 - PE4_16 Corrosion
 - PE4_17 Characterisation methods of materials
 - PE4_18 Environment chemistry
 - PE5 Synthetic Chemistry and Materials
 - ...
 - PE6 Computer Science and Informatics
 - ...
 - PE7 Systems and Communication Engineering
 - ...
 - PE8 Products and Processes Engineering
 - ...
 - PE9 Universe Sciences
 - ...
 - PE10 Earth System Science
 - ...
 - PE11 Materials Engineering
 - ...
- Life Sciences
 - ...
- Social Sciences and Humanities
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- defined in:
https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_Panel_structure_2021_2022.pdf.

Summary:

- Developed by [European Research Council \(ERC\)](#) to categorise research funded by them.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes - very comprehensive and detailed.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.

- Maintained and versioned: This categorisation is primarily focussed on funding policy so when it is updated it may be significantly different. There is no guarantee that it will be of a similar form with any analogous, versioned, mapped terms.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 2 levels.
- PIDs: Numbered identifiers but not semantic – PSDI would need to convert this into a SKOS vocabulary.
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Yes – used in a different context for EU research categorisation – reporting and grant allocation. Researchers who are PSDI contributors and users may have used this classification already when applying for grants (although maybe less common in the UK than EPSRC funding).

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because of the work needed to maintain it in semantic form and because it doesn't show sufficient improvement on other options to do this.

2.11 DFG (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft) classification system of scientific disciplines, research areas and review boards

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- 1 Humanities and Social Sciences
 - ...
- 2 Life Sciences
 - ...
- 3 Natural Sciences
 - 31 Chemistry
 - 3.11 Molecular Chemistry
 - 3.11-01 Inorganic Molecular Chemistry - Synthesis and Characterisation
 - 3.11-02 Organic Molecular Chemistry - Synthesis and Characterisation
 - 3.12 Chemical Solid State and Surface Research
 - 3.12-01 Solid State and Surface Chemistry, Material Synthesis
 - 3.12-02 Physical Chemistry of Solids and Surfaces, Material Characterisation
 - 3.13 Physical Chemistry
 - 3.13-01 Physical Chemistry of Molecules, Liquids and Interfaces, Biophysical Chemistry
 - 3.14 Analytical Chemistry
 - 3.14-01 Analytical Chemistry
 - 3.15 Biological Chemistry and Food Chemistry
 - 3.15-01 Biological and Biomimetic Chemistry
 - 3.15-02 Food Chemistry
 - 3.16 Polymer Research
 - 3.16-01 Preparatory and Physical Chemistry of Polymers
 - 3.16-02 Experimental and Theoretical Physics of Polymers
 - 3.16-03 Polymer Materials
 - 3.17 Theoretical Chemistry
 - 3.17-01 Theoretical Chemistry: Electron Structure, Dynamics, Simulation
 - 3.17-02 Theoretical Chemistry: Molecules, Materials, Surfaces
 - 32 Physics
 - ...
 - 33 Mathematics
 - ...
 - 34 Geosciences
 - ...
- 4 Engineering Sciences
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://www.dfg.de/resource/blob/331950/85717c3edb9ea8bd453d5110849865d3/fachsystematik-2024-2028-en-data.pdf>.
- Converted into browsable ontology form in DFG-Fachsystematik-Ontology: <https://terminology.nfdi4ing.de/ts/ontologies/dfgfo2024/terms>.

Summary:

- Developed by [DFG \(Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft\), German Research Foundation](#).
- This is the structured framework for the German funding body – analogous to the EPSRC research areas, but in a more formal taxonomy.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes - very comprehensive and detailed.
 - Very comprehensive and detailed and logical.
 - Chemistry topics aren't as granular as some of the other candidates.

- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes. It says that it's relevant for 2024-2028 – useful to know its fixed timespan.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 4 levels.
- PIDs: Yes in its DFG-Fachsystematik-Ontology form.
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Yes – used in a different context for German research categorisation – reporting and grant allocation. Also used to browse re3data.org > [Browse by subject](#) (a registry of research data repositories) by subject.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because there are other candidates with a bit more granularity for Chemistry which is important for PSDI.

2.12 Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC)

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- 30 AGRICULTURAL, VETERINARY AND FOOD SCIENCES
 - ...
- 31 BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES
 - ...
- 32 BIOMEDICAL AND CLINICAL SCIENCES
 - ...
- 33 BUILT ENVIRONMENT AND DESIGN
 - ...
- 34 CHEMICAL SCIENCES
 - 3401 Analytical chemistry
 - ...
 - 3402 Inorganic chemistry
 - ...
 - 3403 Macromolecular and materials chemistry
 - ...
 - 3404 Medicinal and biomolecular chemistry
 - ...
 - 3405 Organic chemistry
 - ...
 - 3406 Physical chemistry
 - 340601 Catalysis and mechanisms of reactions
 - 340602 Chemical thermodynamics and energetics
 - 340603 Colloid and surface chemistry
 - 340604 Electrochemistry
 - 340605 Molecular imaging (incl. electron microscopy and neutron diffraction)
 - 340606 Photochemistry
 - 340607 Reaction kinetics and dynamics
 - 340608 Solution chemistry
 - 340609 Transport properties and non-equilibrium processes
 - 340699 Physical chemistry not elsewhere classified
 - 3407 Theoretical and computational chemistry
 - ...
 - 3499 Other chemical sciences
 - ...
- 35 COMMERCE, MANAGEMENT, TOURISM AND SERVICES
 - ...
- 36 CREATIVE ARTS AND WRITING
 - ...
- 37 EARTH SCIENCES
 - ...
- 38 ECONOMICS
 - ...
- 39 EDUCATION
 - ...
- 40 ENGINEERING ...
- 41 ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES ...
- 42 HEALTH SCIENCES ...
- 43 HISTORY, HERITAGE AND ARCHAEOLOGY ...
- 44 HUMAN SOCIETY ...
- 45 INDIGENOUS STUDIES ...
- 46 INFORMATION AND COMPUTING SCIENCES ...
- 47 LANGUAGE, COMMUNICATION AND CULTURE ...
- 48 LAW AND LEGAL STUDIES ...
- 49 MATHEMATICAL SCIENCES ...
- 50 PHILOSOPHY AND RELIGIOUS STUDIES ...
- 51 PHYSICAL SCIENCES ...
- 52 PSYCHOLOGY ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/classifications/australian-and-new-zealand-standard-research-classification-anzsrc/latest-release>.

Summary:

- Published by [Australian Bureau of Statistics](#) which describes it as “a statistical classification used for the measurement and analysis of R&D in Australia and New Zealand”.
- It is the “Fields of Research (FoR)” section which is of particular relevance.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes but we note that, as with some other categorisation schemes, the definition of “physical sciences” is essentially physics and does not contain “chemical sciences”
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes. Original version released 2008, then updated 2020.
- Hierarchical: Yes. 2 digit, 4 digit and 6 digit levels of classification.
- PIDs: Numbered identifiers but not semantic (available as .xlsx files) – PSDI would need to convert this into a SKOS vocabulary.
- Definitions: Yes but very basic. Gives exclusion list for each 4 digit category which is helpful.
- Adoption: Yes. Used by Figshare when browsing by category: https://figshare.com/categories/Physical_sciences/30082.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because of the work needed to maintain it in semantic form and because it doesn't show sufficient improvement on other options to do this.

2.13 The Royal Society Subject Groups and Areas

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- Computer Science
 - ...
- Pure and Applied Mathematics
 - ...
- Astronomy and Physics, Theoretical Physics, Applied Physics
 - ...
- Chemistry, Applied Chemistry, Theoretical Chemistry
 - Chemistry, general
 - Chemistry, organic
 - Chemistry, inorganic
 - Chemistry, physical
 - Chemistry, applied
 - Chemistry, theoretical
 - Chemistry, biological
 - Chemistry, materials
- Engineering, Technology, Instrumentation, Material Science, Experimental Fluid Dynamics
 - ...
- Earth Sciences, Environmental Physical Sciences
 - ...
- Biochemistry, Structural Biology, Molecular Cell Biology
 - ...
- Developmental Biology, Genetics (excl. population genetics), Immunology, Microbiology (excl. medical microbiology)
 - ...
- Anatomy, Physiology, Neurosciences
 - ...
- Organismal Biology, Evolutionary and Ecological Science (incl. soils and agriculture)
 - ...
- Health and Human Sciences
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://royalsociety.org/grants/subject-groups/>.

Summary:

- Developed by [the Royal Society](#) to describe subject groups and areas funded by them.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes but with limitations:
 - Top level categorisation is a bit long-winded.
 - Not granular enough – could do with a level of fields beneath its most granular level.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes.
- Maintained and versioned: This categorisation is devised by the Royal Society to organise its activities so there is a risk that when it is updated it may be very different and may not have analogous, versioned terms.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 2 levels
- PIDs: Numbered identifiers but not semantic (would need making into a SKOS vocabulary).
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Not beyond the Royal Society.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because of the requirements not met (in particular the possibility of it being replaced by something very different going forward).

2.14 Nature Physical Sciences categories

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- Physical sciences
 - Physics
 - Astronomy and planetary science
 - Chemistry
 - Materials science
 - Mathematics and computing
 - Engineering
 - Nanoscience and technology
 - Optics and photonics
 - Energy science and technology
- Earth and environmental sciences
 - ...
- Biological sciences
 - ...
- Health sciences
 - ...
- Scientific community and society
 - ...

Full list is available at:

- <https://www.nature.com/nature/browse-subjects>.

Summary:

- Used by [Nature](#) to classify its publications and journals.
- They tag all articles published in their portfolio according to these categories (unclear whether this is by the author or journal or automatic).

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes:
 - “Physical sciences” definition is broad (not just physics) and includes “Chemistry”.
 - Some PSDI resources would fall under “Earth and environmental sciences”.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes it covers the breadth of our PSDI scope but not in granularity - there is no breakdown of “Chemistry” which is important for PSDI.
- Maintained and versioned: This categorisation is devised by Nature to organise its publications so there is a risk that when it is updated it may be completely different and may not have analogous, versioned terms.
- Hierarchical: Yes – 2 levels
- PIDs: Numbered identifiers but not semantic – PSDI would need to convert this into a SKOS vocabulary.
- Definitions: No.
- Adoption: Not beyond Nature.

Outcomes:

- Not shortlisted because it’s quite a high level of classification and does not provide enough detail.

2.15 “academic discipline” in nfdiCoreOntology

Non-exhaustive example snippet:

- agriculture
- artificial intelligence
- biology
- chemistry
- computer science
- construction engineering
- cybersecurity
- data science
- electrical engineering
- geoscience
- humanity
- materials science
- mathematics
- mechanical engineering
- medicine
- natural science
- physics
- process engineering
- social science
- software engineering
- theoretical computer science

Full list is available at:

- “academic discipline” class within <https://ise-fizkarlsruhe.github.io/nfdicore/>.

Summary:

- Part of [NFDIcore Ontology](#) which is a mid-level BFO ontology for representing metadata related to [NFDI \(Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur\)](#), including individuals, organizations, projects, data portals, and more.
- It is somewhat higher level than we are looking for in PSDI - it is designed to link to more domain-specific ontologies which extend its core structure in a modular fashion e.g. [The MatWerk ontology](#) for Materials Science imports “academic discipline” and adds a class below it “research topic” but these are not enumerated.

Evaluation with respect to requirements:

- Intuitive: Yes.
- Physical Sciences scope: Yes but at a high level – breakdown is not granular enough.
- Maintained and versioned: Yes.
- Hierarchical: It only has one level (which is very high level), but it is of modular design and intended to be extendable below this via linked domain-level ontologies to include more detail.
- PIDs: Yes.
- Definitions: Yes.
- Adoption: Yes at NFDI.

Outcome:

- Not shortlisted because there are alternatives which capture more granularity which is directly integrated within them.

2.16 Higher education teaching classification systems

The following teaching subject classifications were not considered in detail because higher education teaching is not the same as research (and could show some lag in new areas of research), but their grouping systems were considered:

- [HECOS \(Higher Education Classification of Subjects\)](#) and [Common Aggregation Hierarchy \(CAH\)](#) from [HESA \(Higher Education Statistics Agency\)](#)
- [JACS \(Joint Academic Coding System\) Principal subject codes](#) from [HESA \(Higher Education Statistics Agency\)](#) (replaced by HECOS/CAH).
- [Classification of Instructional Programs](#) (U.S. Department of Education's National Center for Education Statistics (NCES)).
- [Australian Standard Classification of Education](#) (Australian bureau of statistics)
- HESA (Higher Education Statistics Agency) classify academic staff according to their departments as described by [Cost centres \(2012/13 onwards\)](#)

2.17 Library classification systems

The following library classifications were not considered in detail because library content is not the same as research (and could show some lag in new areas of research), but their grouping systems were considered:

- [Library of Congress Classification](#)
- [Dewey Decimal Classification](#)
- [Cambridge University Library Classification](#)

3 Mapping of PSDI resource themes onto shortlisted candidates

This extensive review of how subjects are described and classified in section 2 was useful not only in the selection of candidates, but also to observe recurring successful themes in their organisation. In particular, we observed that the general organisation system below was common and very intuitive to follow:

- domain (e.g. Physical Sciences, Natural Sciences, Applied Sciences etc.)
 - o subject discipline (e.g. Chemistry, Physics)
 - sub-discipline (e.g. Organic Chemistry, Inorganic Chemistry)
 - field (more specific description of field).

In PSDI it is not necessary to include the top-level since our scope generally corresponds to one subject grouping – the Physical Sciences. Hence, in our mapping process described in this section we also illustrate how for each candidate, a subset of the hierarchical grouping can be simplified to a consistent, 2-level hierarchy with subject discipline at the top-level and sub-disciplines within this (a recurring and sensible structure) which then contain the more specific fields.

This section shows the mapping of PSDI resource themes (or resources) onto each shortlisted categorisation system. This allows us to evaluate requirement 1 (intuitive) in more detail.

Note that:

- We only include resource themes (and resources) which were in PSDI as of August 2025.
- Mapping is performed at the resource theme level and can be assumed to apply to all resources within them, unless a resource has a distinct theme to its parent resource theme in some way (usually more specific) in which case they are included explicitly.
- For hierarchical classification systems, a resource theme is assigned to the most relevant term, regardless of the level of the hierarchy. For some resource themes this will be a general term near the top of the hierarchy e.g. “chemistry” but for some it will be a more specific term e.g. at the most granular level of the classification.
- We have simplified the hierarchies shown to a maximum of 2-levels to reflect the filters that will be shown in the PSDI “What we provide” pages (more levels become unwieldy and complicated for users). If the exact term that is relevant for a PSDI resource theme is more granular than level 2, the dcat:theme column indicates the term that would be shown on the resource/resource theme page itself (only Level 1 and 2 would show in the PSDI “What We Provide” filters though, and not this dcat:theme).
- This simplified hierarchy follows the general structure:
 - o Level 1 corresponds to discipline.
 - o Level 2 corresponds to sub-discipline.
 - o dcat:theme corresponds to specific term (if not one of the above).
- It is possible for a resource or resource theme to appear more than once, if multiple subject terms are appropriate.
- If a resource theme is not specific to a particular dcat:theme value, or defined set of dcat:themes, they are indicated as “Multidisciplinary”.
- We have also simplified the hierarchies shown to only include the subset of classifications which are relevant to PSDI. Where required, we will add the top Level 1 term “Other” to contain terms which do not correspond to those explicitly shown for Level 1 (to simplify the options presented to the user when searching). Again, this is just for the purposes of the folder structure of the subject filters, and the dcat:theme values of these resource themes would still the properly defined term. There should not be many of these, since they would be at the edges of PSDI’s scope.

The mapping shown in the subsequent sections are outlined in the accompanying file PSDI_Subject_Shortlist_Mappings.xlsx which lists:

- “PSDI resource themes” – the PSDI resource themes and the URLs that describe them as of August 2025 which were mapped in this exercise
- “PSDI_Domains_derivation” – the list of PSDI domains described in section 2.1 and details of their derivation
- “1_EuroSciVoc” – mapping described in [section 3.1](#).
- “2_ModSci” – mapping described in [section 3.2](#).
- “3_OpenAlex” – mapping described in [section 3.3](#).

3.1 Mapping of PSDI resource themes and PSDI Domain categories onto EuroSciVoc categories

Level 1	Level 2	dcat:theme	PSDI Domains	PSDI resource themes
earth and related environmental sciences				
		environmental sciences	- Environmental	
mathematics				
biological sciences				
		molecular biology	- Chemical Biology	- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
		biochemistry	- Biochemistry	
chemical sciences				- PSDI Data Revival - Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - PSDI Data Conversion
		organic chemistry	- Chemistry Materials - Organic & Pharmaceutical	- Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Chemical Availability Search (ChASe); Propersea (Property Prediction); Chemotion Repository - Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
		inorganic chemistry	- Chemistry Materials	- Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows
		organometallic chemistry	- Metal Organic	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
		physical chemistry	- Physical Chemistry	- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)
		quantum chemistry		
		polymer sciences	- Polymers - Chemistry Materials	
		Catalysis	- Catalysis - Chemistry Materials	- Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows
		analytical chemistry	- Analytical Chemistry	
physics (physical sciences)				
		condensed matter physics	- Solid-state Physics	- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
		soft matter physics		- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
		Optics		
		microscopy		
		nonlinear optics		- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Resurrecting Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Case Study
		absorption spectroscopy		- Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
computer and information sciences			- Computational	
		artificial intelligence		
		machine learning		- Data to Knowledge
		Software		
		software development		- PSDI Skills4Scientists - Python I; Python II; Version Control and Github
		simulation software		- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)
		data science		
		data exchange		- PSDI Data Conversion - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Data Revival
		data processing		- PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Galaxy

	computational science			- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling
engineering and technology				
	chemical engineering	- Chemical Engineering		
	other engineering and technologies	- Food		
	environmental engineering	- Sustainability & Energy		
	nanotechnology	- Nanotech		
	materials engineering	- Engineering Materials		
	crystals			- OPTIMADE Data Providers - Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
other				
multidisciplinary		- Methods		- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Container Image Registry - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Galaxy - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Knowledge Base Topics - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)

Note that:

- The level 1 classifications broadly correspond to the NT1 level of EuroSciVoc, and level 2 to NT2, apart from “engineering and technology” which is a top-level OECD FORD/FOS term (and its sub-disciplines are taken at the NT1 level).
- We have renamed “physical sciences” to “physics” to avoid confusion in PSDI’s context.
- We have adjusted some of these EuroSciVoc term assignments for resources compared to that published in PSDI currently in light of this review.
- Edge cases to highlight:
 - “OPTIMADE Data Providers” and “Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)” moved from “crystallography” (under “geology”) to “crystals” (under “materials engineering”).
 - There is no “computer model” or “simulation” term for e.g. “Data Collections for Chemical Modelling” and many other resources.

3.2 Mapping of PSDI resource themes and PSDI Domain categories onto ModSci categories

Level 1	Level 2	dcat:theme	PSDI Domains	PSDI resource themes
Computer Science			- Computational	
	Artificial Intelligence			
	Machine Learning			- Data to Knowledge
	modsci#ComputerApplications			- Container Image Registry
	modsci#ComputerSoftware			- PSDI Skills4Scientists - Python I; Python II; Version Control and Github - BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
	modsci#DataFormat			- PSDI Data Conversion - PSDI Data Revival - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources
Engineering				
Mathematics				
Scientific Modelling			- Computational	- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Data to Knowledge - Galaxy
Biology				
	Biochemistry		- Biochemistry	
	Molecular Biology		- Chemical Biology	- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
Chemistry				- PSDI Data Revival - Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - PSDI Data Conversion
	Analytical Chemistry		- Analytical Chemistry	
	Biochemistry		- Biochemistry	
	Chemical Engineering		- Chemical Engineering	
	Crystallography			
	Environmental Chemistry		- Environmental	
	Food Chemistry		- Food	
	Green Chemistry		- Environmental - Sustainability & Energy	
	Inorganic Chemistry			- Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows
	Materials Science		- Chemistry Materials - Engineering Materials	
	modsci_Nanochemistry		- Nanotech	
	modsci_Polymerisation Mechanisms		- Polymers	
	modsci_TheoryAndDesignOfMaterials			- OPTIMADE Data Providers
	Organic Chemistry		- Organic & Pharmaceutical	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Chemical Availability Search (ChASE); Propersea (Property Prediction); Chemotion Repository

	Organometallic Chemistry		- Metal Organic	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) - Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)
	Physical Chemistry		- Physical Chemistry	- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)
		modsci_Catalysis	- Catalysis	- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows
Earth Science				
	Environmental Science		- Environmental	
Physics				
	Condensed Matter Physics		- Solid-state Physics	- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
		modsci_OpticalPhysics		
		modsci_NonlinearOptics		- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Resurrecting Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Case Study
		modsci_Spectroscopy		- Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
other				
multidisciplinary				
			- Methods	- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Container Image Registry - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Galaxy - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Knowledge Base Topics - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)

Note that:

- The Level 1 classifications broadly correspond to the 2nd level under [Science](#) and Level 2 to the level directly under that.
- Edge cases to highlight:
 - The definition for [Physical Chemistry](#) mentions “quantum chemistry” but this is not listed under it so e.g. “Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)” needs to be tagged with this more general term.

3.3 Mapping of PSDI resource themes and PSDI Domain categories onto OpenAlex categories

Level 1	Level 2	dcat:theme	PSDI Domains	PSDI resource themes
Agricultural and Biological Sciences				
	Food Science		- Food	
Biochemistry, Genetics and Molecular Biology				
	Biochemistry		- Biochemistry	
	Molecular Biology		- Chemical Biology	
		Protein Structure and Dynamics		- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
Chemical Engineering				
	Bioengineering			
		Nanotechnology research and applications	- Nanotechnology	
	Catalysis		- Catalysis	- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Catalysis Data Infrastructure (CDI) Database - Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - PSDI Data Conversion - PSDI Data Revival
Chemistry				
	Analytical Chemistry		- Analytical Chemistry	
	Electrochemistry			
	Inorganic Chemistry			
		Crystal structures of chemical compounds		- OPTIMADE Data Providers - Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
		Zeolite Catalysis and Synthesis		- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Catalysis Data Infrastructure (CDI) Database
	Organic Chemistry		- Organic & Pharmaceutical	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Chemical Availability Search (ChASe), Propersea (Property Prediction)
		Organometallic Complex Synthesis and Catalysis		- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Catalysis Data Infrastructure (CDI) Database - Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)
		Organometallic Compounds Synthesis and Characterization	- Metal Organic	
		Chemical Thermodynamics and Molecular Structure		- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection
	Physical and Theoretical Chemistry		- Physical Chemistry	
		Advanced Physical and Chemical Molecular Interactions		
		thermodynamics and calorimetric analyses		- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection
	Spectroscopy			- Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation

		Advanced NMR Techniques and Applications			- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC)
Computer Science				- Computational	
	Artificial Intelligence				
		Machine Learning and Algorithms			- Data to Knowledge
	Computational Theory and Mathematics				
		Modeling and Simulation Systems			- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
	Computer Science Applications				
		Teaching and Learning Programming			- PSDI Skills4Scientists - Python I; Python II; Version Control and Github
	Information Systems				
		Advanced Technology in Applications			
		Research Data Management Practices			- PSDI Data Conversion - PSDI Data Revival - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Galaxy
Earth and Planetary Sciences					
Energy				- Sustainability & Energy	
Engineering					
	Mechanics of Materials			- Engineering Materials	
		Muon and positron interactions and applications			- Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
Environmental Science				- Environmental	
Materials Science					
	Electronic, Optical and Magnetic Materials				
		Nonlinear Optical Materials Research			- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Resurrecting Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Case Study - OPTIMADE Data Providers
	Materials Chemistry			- Chemistry Materials	
		Mesoporous Materials and Catalysis			- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example) - Catalysis Data Infrastructure (CDI) Database - Data to Knowledge
		Machine Learning in Materials Science			
	Polymers and Plastics			- Polymers	
Mathematics					
Physics and Astronomy					
	Condensed Matter Physics			- Solid-state Physics	- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Galaxy Training Network: Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
		Theoretical and Computational Physics			

	Advanced Condensed Matter Physics		
other			
multidisciplinary		- Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Container Image Registry - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Galaxy - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Knowledge Base Topics - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)

Note that:

- The level 1 classifications correspond to the “field_name” level of OpenAlex topics, and level 2 to its “subfield_name”.
- Edge cases to highlight:
 - “Cambridge Structural Database (CSD)” is in “Crystal structures of chemical compounds” but note that this is under “Inorganic Chemistry”.
 - There are 35 topics which contain “nano” which are within “Materials Science”, “Engineering”, “Chemistry”, “Physics and Astronomy”, “Pharmacology, Toxicology and Pharmaceutics”, “Earth and Planetary Sciences”.

4 Conclusions

Out of the 3 shortlisted candidates, ModSci was ranked third. It was the most semantic option of the three candidates (it is compatible with [Basic Formal Ontology \(BFO\)](#) ontologies), has good chemistry representation, and is used by [SciData](#) which may be useful in the future when we consider capturing data-level metadata in PSDI. However, when the details of its application to PSDI resources were explored it was apparent that this would require some further development to be of use for PSDI e.g. it would be necessary to add labels to terms of interest to us, and the Computer Science section would need some attention. As a result our focus turned to the other two candidates, which are more complete than this ontology and would not need such development.

OpenAlex topics were ranked second. The consistent nature of the top three levels (based on the [All Science Journal Classifications \(ASJC\)](#) structure of [Scopus](#)) – domain, field and subfield - are very well organised and intuitive, but the 3rd level (topic) were hard to assign resources to because there were so many of them, they were very specific, and sometimes very similar topic names were in very different parts of the hierarchy. If PSDI were to use it to capture dcat:theme we would need to set up additional pipelines and tools (as described in the “Outcomes” section of [section 2.5](#)) to publish the OpenAlex topics in a semantic format compatible with our metadata, and aid resource owners when assigning topics to their resources (subject to their adjustment and approval). This would be an interesting route to investigate in the future, as LLM methods improve, and PSDI metadata technical architecture progresses.

As a result, for now PSDI will continue using EuroSciVoc to capture dcat:theme of resource themes or resources but will add a hierarchy to group these in filter user interfaces. This classification system can describe PSDI resources across PSDI’s scope to a good level of detail, is available in semantic form and is compatible with OECD’s FORD/FOS which is used in a lot of reporting. In light of our review of different categorisation systems, we feel that the full EuroSciVoc hierarchy is quite complicated to navigate and suggest streamlining it to (a) make it more navigable and (b) focus it to reflect the PSDI domain categorisations. This suggested subset of the EuroSciVoc hierarchy is shown in [section 3.1](#) with the following features:

- It uses different levels of EuroSciVoc depending on their relevance to PSDI.
- Its top level reflects common disciplines within the PSDI scope (EPSRC funding scope). This limits the top level to a manageable, limited set of familiar terms.
- Disciplines which are not in this scope can be included using the top-level “Other” folder.
- A top-level “multidisciplinary” folder will contain resources that are tagged with general dcat:theme values [[natural sciences](#) and [engineering and technology](#)].
- The second-layer shows breakdown of disciplines into subdisciplines but only for disciplines which are key focus of PSDI than those on the periphery.
- We will rename “physical sciences” to “physics” in this hierarchy to avoid confusion in the context of PSDI.
- The folders reflect PSDI domains – most of those correspond to a category at the top or second layer here.
- We will only include the subset of hierarchy which contain PSDI resources – no dead-ends (as PSDI gains more resources, then more categories will be added in line with these guidelines as necessary).

When implemented, the updated subject classification will be viewable at:
<https://metadata.psd.ac.uk/>, [PSDI What We Provide](#) and [PSDI Cross Data Search](#).

Appendix 1: Derivation of PSDI domain categories

Categories of physical science derived from analysis of: [Institution of Chemical Engineers \(IChemE\) special interest groups](#); [Royal Society of Chemistry \(RSC\) interest groups](#); [Institute of Physics \(IOP\) special interest groups](#); and [Royal Society of Chemistry \(RSC\) journals](#).

PSDI Domain category	RSC interest groups	IChemE special interest groups	IOP special interest groups	RSC journals
Environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water Science - Agriculture - Environmental Chemistry - Radiochemistry - Toxicology Group - Astrochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water - Environment and Clean Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental Science: Atmospheres - Environmental Science: Nano - Environmental Science: Advances - Energy & Environmental Science - Environmental Science: Water Research & Technology - Environmental Science: Processes & Impacts
Chemical Engineering	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Process Chemistry & Technology Group - Industrial Physical Chemistry - Particle Characterisation - Formulation Science & Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pharma - Biochemical Engineering - Sustainability - Clean Energy - Oil, Gas and Energy Transition - Particle Technology 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molecular Systems Design & Engineering - Industrial Chemistry & Materials - Reaction Chemistry & Engineering
Sustainability & Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy - Electrochemistry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainability - Clean Energy - Oil, Gas and Energy Transition - Nuclear Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy - Nuclear Industry - Nuclear Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainability - Sustainable Energy & Fuels - Energy Advances - EES Solar - Journal of Materials Chemistry A - Green Chemistry - EES Batteries
Solid-state Physics			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theory of Condensed Matter - Structural Condensed Matter Physics - Superconductivity - Quantum Electronics and Photonics - Magnetism - Atomic and Molecular Interactions - Quantum Optics, Quantum Information and Quantum Control - Semiconductor Physics - Materials and Characterisation 	

PSDI Domain category	RSC interest groups	IChemE special interest groups	IOP special interest groups	RSC journals
Polymers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polymer Physics - Macro Group UK 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polymer Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Polymer Chemistry - RSC Applied Polymers
Physical Chemistry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Spectroscopy and Dynamics - Photophysics & Photochemistry Group - Stat. Mech. & Thermodynamics - Gas Kinetics 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molecular Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Faraday Discussions - RSC Applied Interfaces - Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics
Catalysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applied Catalysis - Surface Reactivity & Catalysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Catalysis and Reaction Engineering 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Catalysis Science & Technology - EES Catalysis
Chemistry Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solid State Chemistry - British Carbon - Applied Materials Chemistry 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thin Films and Surfaces - British Carbon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Journal of Materials Chemistry B - Materials Advances - Materials Chemistry Frontiers - Materials Horizons - Journal of Materials Chemistry A - Journal of Materials Chemistry C
Engineering Materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Applied Materials Chemistry - British Carbon 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Thin Films and Surfaces - British Carbon 	
Nanotech	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemical Nanoscience and Nanotechnology 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nanoscale Physics and Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nanoscale - Nanoscale Advances - Nanoscale Horizons - Lab on a Chip
Metal Organic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Main Group Chemistry - Porous Materials - Radiochemistry - Inorganic Biochemistry - Coordination & Organometallic Chemistry Discussion - Inorganic Reaction Mechanisms - Macrocyclic & Supramolecular Chemistry 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inorganic Chemistry Frontiers - Dalton Transactions
Computational	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theoretical Chemistry - Chemical Information & Computer Applications 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Computational Physics - Mathematical and Theoretical Physics 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Digital Discovery

PSDI Domain category	RSC interest groups	IChemE special interest groups	IOP special interest groups	RSC journals
Organic & Pharmaceutical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Heterocyclic & Synthesis - Physical Organic Chemistry - Macrocyclic & Supramolecular Chemistry - Joint Pharmaceutical Analysis - Fluorine Chemistry - Carbohydrate 	- Pharma		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RSC Pharmaceutics - Organic Chemistry Frontiers - Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry
Chemical Biology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chemical Biology & Bioorganic - Biological & Medicinal Chemistry - Carbohydrate 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Natural Product Reports - RSC Chemical Biology - Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry - Journal of Materials Chemistry B - Biomaterials Science - RSC Medicinal Chemistry
Biochemistry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protein & Peptide Science - Biotechnology - Radiochemistry - Inorganic Biochemistry - Biomaterials Chemistry - Nucleic Acids - Biophysical Chemistry 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organic & Biomolecular Chemistry - Biomaterials Science - RSC Medicinal Chemistry
Analytical Chemistry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analytical Biosciences - Microanalytical - Automation & Analytical Management - Water Science - Separation Science - Thermal Methods - Electroanalytical Sensing Systems 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Molecular Omics - Analyst - Analytical Methods - Sensors & Diagnostics - Journal of Analytical Atomic Spectrometry
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Atomic Spectroscopy - Molecular Spectroscopy - ESR Spectroscopy - NMR Discussion - Neutron Scattering 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - British Radiofrequency Spectroscopy - Neutron Scattering - Electron Microscopy and Analysis - Instrument Science and Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CrystEngComm - RSC Mechanochemistry
Food	- Food	- Food and Drink	- Food Physics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sustainable Food Technology - Food & Function

Appendix 2: Mapping of PSDI resource themes onto PSDI domain categories

PSDI domain category	PSDI resource theme
Environmental	
Chemical Engineering	
Sustainability & Energy	
Solid-state Physics	- Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Resurrecting Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Case Study
Polymers	
Physical Chemistry	- Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Physical Chemistry Properties Data Collection - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Resurrecting Second Harmonic Generation (SHG) Case Study
Catalysis	- Galaxy - Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)
Chemistry Materials	- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Galaxy Training Network: Example Galaxy XAFS RO-Crate Workflows; Finding the Muon Stopping Site; MuDirac Documentation; MuSpinSim Documentation; Xray Larch Documentation
Engineering Materials	
Nanotech	
Metal Organic	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) - Thematic Portal (Catalysis Data Infrastructure Example)
Computational	- Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - Data to Knowledge - Galaxy - BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Propersea (Property Prediction)
Organic & Pharmaceutical	- Cambridge Structural Database (CSD) - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - Making Electronic Supplementary Information (ESI) Machine-Readable Case Study - Data Collections for Chemical Modelling - Collaborative Computational Project for NMR Crystallography (CCP-NC) - PSDI Data Revival - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - Chemical Availability Search (ChASe); Propersea (Property Prediction)
Chemical Biology	
Biochemistry	- BioSim (Biomolecular Simulations) Data Resources
Analytical Chemistry	
Methods	
Food	
Multidisciplinary	- PSDI Data Conversion - PSDI Knowledge Base Topics - Case Studies: Discovering Value in Legacy Data - PSDI Digital Lab Notebook Resources - PSDI Skills4Scientists - Container Image Registry - Data Sources for PSDI Cross Data Search - OPTIMADE Data Providers